

Figure 8: The 12x12 vāstu, PI 8.185-195b.

1 Brahmā	19 Satya	37 Roga
2 Marīcaka	20 Bhṛśa	38 Vāyu
3 Vivasvant	21 Antarikṣa	39 Nāga
4 Mitra	22 Agni	40 Mukhya
5 Pṛthivīdhara	23 Pūṣan	41 Bhallāṭa
6 Āpa	24 Vitatha	42 Soma
7 Āpavatsa	25 Gṛhakṣata	43 Ṛgi
8 Savitr	26 Yama	44 Aditi
9 Sāvitrī	27 Gandharva	45 Diti
10 Indra	28 Bhṛṅga	46 Skanda
11 Indrajit	29 Mṛga	47 Aryaman
12 Rudra	30 Piṭṛ	48 Jambha
13 Rudradāsa	31 Dauvārika	49 Pilipiccha
14 Īśa	32 Sugrīva	50 Carakī
15 Parjanya	33 Puṣpadanta	51 Vidārī
16 Jaya	34 Pracetas	52 Pūtanā
17 Mahendra	35 Asura	53 Pāparākṣasī
18 Sūrya	36 Śoṣa	

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53		49				50		
	38					45	14	
	39	40	41	42	43	44		
	37						15	
48	36	13		5	7		16	
	35	12			6		17	
	34	4		1	2		18	
	33	10		3	9		19	
	32	11			8		20	
	31			26			21	
	30	29	28	27	25	24	23	22
52		47				51		